

SCOPE: Stakeholder Consensus for Operational Pre-implementation Evidence

A modified Nominal Group Technique for health innovation evaluation design

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Abstract

Background

Economic and outcomes models for novel health innovations rest on operational assumptions about how a service would function in a target health system. Where the innovation does not yet exist in that context, those assumptions cannot be derived from observational data and have no established methodology for their production through stakeholder consensus. This leaves models vulnerable to challenge on structural grounds during formal health technology appraisal. We describe the development and application of SCOPE (Stakeholder Consensus for Operational Pre-implementation Evidence), a modified Nominal Group Technique designed to generate defensible operational specifications for novel health innovations before implementation.

Methods

SCOPE was developed during an adaptive process whilst developing a mobile stroke unit pathway and modelling, and employs a sequential three-round workshop structure in which operational specifications are developed iteratively across interconnected domains, reflecting the complexity of health system contexts in which novel services must function. Key modifications to standard NGT include an iterative multi-round structure for interconnected decisions, explicit classification of non-consensus outcomes into a three-tier uncertainty framework, and transparent documentation enabling independent evaluation of model structure. Three online rounds were conducted with 15 interdisciplinary stakeholders using a pre-specified consensus threshold of 80%.

Results

Consensus was achieved on 14 of 20 operational specifications across dispatch, staffing, treatment eligibility, and conveyance domains, providing a defensible structural foundation for subsequent economic modelling. Six non-consensus items were systematically classified: five as third-order uncertainty requiring scenario analysis in subsequent modelling, and one (geographic base location) as an irreducible trade-off between equity and efficiency requiring explicit value judgement by decision-makers. Vote distributions, classification rationale, and modelling implications are reported for all six items.

Conclusions

SCOPE grounds the structural assumptions of health economic and outcomes models in documented stakeholder consensus, enabling independent assessment of model structure quality and providing systematic guidance on how non-consensus items should be treated in subsequent modelling. Having been instantiated in a single complex case, prospective application across different innovation types and health system settings is required to establish its generalisability. The methodology should be applicable to any health innovation requiring operational specification before formal evaluation, regardless of health system context, and implementation resources are provided as supplementary materials.

Background

Why innovations fail to reach patients

Health innovations regularly fail to reach the patients who would benefit from them. Greenhalgh et al.'s systematic review of diffusion of innovations in health service organisations found that most empirical work focused on short-term adoption of simple innovations by individual adopters, with little examination of complex innovations requiring organisational decision-making, sustained budgets, and system-level implementation [28]. Later work developing the NASSS framework identified complexity in the innovation, the adopting organisation, and the wider system as the consistent predictor of non adoption, abandonment, and failure to scale [29]. The evidence for efficacy is rarely the problem. What is more often missing is a systematic account of how the innovation would operate as a service.

This matters more for some innovations than others. Health systems are complex adaptive systems: their components interact non-linearly, decisions are interdependent, and the system responds to interventions in ways that cannot be predicted from individual components alone [30]. In complex systems, the operational form of a novel service cannot be read off from trial evidence or prior experience elsewhere. It must be specified through engagement with the system in which the service will operate, and it must be built iteratively, because the interdependencies between operational decisions only surface when they are worked through together.

Stroke care illustrates this. The development of mechanical thrombectomy as a treatment for large vessel occlusion transformed acute stroke management and generated a cascade of downstream innovations, each requiring operational specification before evaluation or implementation at scale: mobile stroke units to accelerate time to treatment, video triage to extend specialist reach, point-of-care testing including D-dimer assays to rule conditions in and out at the scene, and AI tools to support scan interpretation without an on-site specialist. Each shares the same problem. The clinical case may be established. The operational case has not been.

The limits of upstream methods

Upstream activities address part of this problem. Early HTA, horizon scanning, value propositions, and innovation briefings assess whether an innovation is promising enough to warrant further investment. Their limitation is not that they ignore operational questions but that they address them at the level of concept rather than specification. An early HTA can establish that mobile stroke units reduce time to thrombolysis in urban trial settings. It cannot establish how an MSU should be dispatched across diverse ambulance service geographies, what staffing configuration is sustainable under NHS rota pressures, or how the service integrates with existing stroke pathway infrastructure. These questions need answers before a model can be built and before a commissioner can act.

Value propositions are constructed from the perspective of the technology developer, making the case for adoption across potential markets. This is rational practice. It means that the evidence supporting an innovation reflects conditions chosen to demonstrate efficacy, which may differ from the conditions of sustained NHS operational deployment. The NHS occupies a specific position in any developer's market: one potential adopter among several, with operational pressures, workforce constraints, geographic complexity, and accountability requirements that may not match the trial or deployment contexts in which the innovation's value was established. No existing methodology is designed to translate a developer's value proposition into an NHS-viable operational specification.

Standard NGT and Delphi were not designed for this task. Delphi originated as a forecasting tool outside healthcare; NGT as an organisational planning method [5], both later adapted for clinical guideline development and research prioritisation [6, 7, 8, 9]. Both are single-pass methods, conceived before complexity science entered health systems thinking [30]. In complex systems, single-pass methods are insufficient: decisions are interconnected, and the answer to each depends on answers that have not yet been reached. Structured expert elicitation frameworks assume operational structure already exists [27]. Evidence development frameworks support pathway analysis for innovations inserting into existing care models [10, 11, 12]. Co-design approaches work best with existing services [13, 14]. Implementation science frameworks address how to implement once what is being implemented has been defined [15, 16]. Table 1 maps these methods against the requirements that operational co-development demands.

Table 1: Existing methods mapped against requirements for operational co-development of health innovations

Method	Addresses operational design	Handles multiple interconnected decisions	Pre-implementation context	Classifies uncertainty types	Auditable trail for model credibility	Patient / public involvement
Standard NGT	No	No	No	No	No	No
Delphi	No	Partial	No	No	No	No
SHELF / structured expert elicitation	No	No	No	Partial	Partial	No
Evidence development frameworks [10]	Partial	No	Partial	No	No	No
Co-design [13, 14]	Partial	Partial	No	No	No	Yes
Implementation science frameworks [15, 16]	No	No	No	No	No	Partial

Method	Addresses operational design	Handles multiple interconnected decisions	Pre-implementation context	Classifies uncertainty types	Auditable trail for model credibility	Patient / public involvement
SCOPE (modified NGT)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

NGT = Nominal Group Technique. SHELF = Sheffield Elicitation Framework. Partial = addresses some but not all aspects of this requirement.

The ACCORD guideline for reporting consensus methods in biomedicine provides a 35-item framework applicable across consensus methodologies [25]. The methodology described in this paper is designed to be reported in accordance with ACCORD.

The gap in the evidence development pathway

Health innovations move through a recognisable evidence development pathway. Early signals of potential lead to horizon scanning and early HTA, which establish whether an innovation is worth further investment. Formal evaluation follows for those that are: economic modelling, clinical trials, health technology appraisal. Adoption and implementation follow from that. Each stage has established methods. What the pathway lacks is a systematic method for the step between early HTA and formal evaluation: generating the operational specification that evaluation requires.

Early HTA establishes promise. It does not establish how the innovation would operate. Value propositions, as Graziadio et al. identify, are constructed from the developer's perspective to make the case for adoption [10]. They are not designed to answer the operational questions that a potential adopter and a formal evaluator need answered: how the service would be staffed, dispatched, integrated, and configured for the specific health system context in which it would run. When formal evaluation begins without those answers, the model that underpins it rests on assumptions that have not been derived through any systematic process. Those assumptions are then available for challenge by NICE committees, peer reviewers, or commissioners at the point where challenge is most costly.

The methodology described in this paper sits at this gap: upstream of formal evaluation, downstream of early HTA, and designed for the pre-implementation specification that neither stage currently provides.

The epistemological case

Pearl establishes that causal model structure must be asserted, not discovered [31]. In pre-implementation contexts no outcome data exists, no single expert holds sufficient knowledge across the domains that operational design requires, and interconnected decisions cannot be specified in a single pass. A structured, iterative, multi-stakeholder process is therefore not a methodological preference but the only means by which distributed knowledge can be

elicited, aggregated, and translated into a defensible model structure when no observational data exists.

In complex health systems, the boundaries between professional knowledge domains are precisely where the assumptions that determine model structure are located. What is clinically desirable cannot be separated from what is operationally viable, which cannot be separated from what can be modelled, which cannot be separated from what patients will accept. These questions cannot be answered sequentially by different domain experts and combined afterwards. Working within a single domain means making assumptions about what lies outside it, and those assumptions may be wrong in ways not visible from within the domain. Iterative cross-domain elicitation surfaces those assumptions progressively and tests them against each other. Each round reveals interdependencies that were not visible in the previous one.

Not everything that emerges from this process can be directly modelled. Some specifications are too context-dependent to translate into nationally applicable parameters. Others require local clinical judgement rather than fixed values. Identifying what cannot or should not be specified nationally is itself a valuable output: it tells the modeller to treat something as a sensitivity or as a locally determined variable rather than a fixed assumption. The non-consensus items document where cross-domain testing revealed genuine irresolvable differences. That record is part of what gives the model structure its evidential standing.

Patient and public involvement is epistemically necessary in this process, not merely an inclusion requirement. Patients hold knowledge about the acceptability, equity implications, and lived experience of a proposed service that is not available from within any professional domain. In the MSU application this was demonstrated directly: the geographic equity dimension of the base location decision, which became the study's only irreducible trade-off, was articulated most clearly by PPI representatives. Without them in the process, that conflict would either not have surfaced or would have been resolved by professional assumption rather than documented as a genuine value conflict requiring decision-maker judgement.

NHS standards for stakeholder-inclusive evidence development add a further requirement. Operational specifications derived without structured stakeholder engagement cannot be defended before NICE committees, peer reviewers, or commissioners who have standing to question the assumptions on which a model rests. Transparency and auditability are not optional features of a pre-implementation specification process. They are what gives the outputs evidential standing.

Aim

This paper describes the development of a methodology for generating stakeholder consensus on operational specifications for novel health innovations before implementation, grounded in complexity theory and the epistemological framework established by Pearl, and designed to meet NHS standards for transparent, auditable, stakeholder-inclusive evidence

development. We demonstrate its application to Mobile Stroke Unit pathway development for NHS England and Wales: a complex, multi-stakeholder, pre-implementation context that provides a demanding test of the methodology. The cascade of innovations generated by mechanical thrombectomy illustrates both the scope of the problem and the generalisability of the methodology to related innovations in the same pathway.

Methods

Study design and rationale

Standard NGT was developed by Delbecq, Van de Ven, and Gustafson for organisational programme planning [5]: groups with relevant knowledge generate and prioritise ideas through structured silent generation, round-robin sharing, clarification discussion, and individual voting. It has since been applied to clinical guideline development and research prioritisation [6, 7, 8, 9]. In these applications it performs well because the problems it addresses are, in the complexity science sense, simple or complicated: the solution space is bounded, decisions are largely independent, and expertise can be aggregated in a structured single session.

Operational design for a novel health service in a complex health system is a different kind of problem. Decisions are interconnected: staffing determines capacity, capacity constrains operating hours, operating hours affect dispatch protocols, dispatch protocols interact with existing ambulance service operations. These interdependencies cannot be resolved in a single session because the answer to each question depends on answers that have not yet been reached. Iteration is not a methodological convenience. It is what the complexity of the problem requires.

Three modifications to standard NGT follow from this. The multi-round sequential structure allows decisions to be developed iteratively, with each round building on the last. The mixed stakeholder design ensures that operational knowledge held by clinicians, service managers, and patients is integrated alongside clinical knowledge, because viable service design requires both. The uncertainty classification framework translates non-consensus outcomes into specific guidance for subsequent modelling, distinguishing decisions requiring scenario analysis from those requiring sensitivity analysis and those requiring explicit value judgements by decision-makers.

MSU pathway development was selected as the exemplar case for several reasons. No operational pathway existed for NHS England and Wales, meaning stakeholders had to design operations prospectively rather than refine existing ones. The innovation required specification across multiple interconnected domains including dispatch, staffing, treatment eligibility, conveyance, and service integration. It required integration of clinical, operational, and patient perspectives that pulled in different directions. And operational specifications

would feed directly into economic modelling [19] and inform commissioning decisions, making model structure credibility a practical requirement.

A more demanding exemplar provides a stronger test of a new methodology. Research teams applying this methodology to less complex innovations should find the process more straightforward.

Team composition

The methodology requires a team whose skills span domains that do not typically coexist in HTA or evidence development research groups. Several distinct capabilities are needed.

Qualitative facilitation of multi-stakeholder workshops is a distinct skill from standard qualitative research. It requires real-time management of group dynamics across professional and patient participants, productive handling of disagreement without premature closure, and simultaneous documentation of emerging specifications. The facilitator also needs sufficient understanding of modelling requirements to recognise when a specification is too vague to be analytically useful and to ask the right questions in the moment to sharpen it.

Qualitative analysis using structured methods such as framework analysis is needed between rounds to translate workshop outputs into a coherent developing pathway. This requires both analytical expertise and sufficient clinical knowledge to assess whether emerging specifications are coherent.

Clinical domain expertise is needed to engage credibly with professional participants on technical pathway decisions and to assess whether specifications are clinically sound. This person also needs to be willing to engage with operational constraints that qualify or complicate the clinical ideal.

Modelling expertise is needed to ensure that specifications are produced in a form that is analytically usable, not just clinically meaningful. Some specifications will be too vague, too context-dependent, or expressed in language that does not map onto model parameters. The modeller's presence during the process is what prevents specifications from being clinically coherent but analytically unusable.

The interaction between these skills matters as much as the skills themselves. The modeller needs enough understanding of qualitative process to recognise when apparent consensus reflects genuine agreement rather than deference or fatigue. The facilitator needs enough understanding of modelling to know when to push for greater precision. In the MSU application these functions were distributed across the team, with LM and JS leading facilitation and analysis, MJ providing clinical domain knowledge, and MA representing modelling requirements. The Miro board served as a shared representational space in which emerging specifications were visible to all participants simultaneously, enabling real-time correction across professional boundaries.

Patient and public involvement is not an add-on to this process. It is epistemically necessary, for the reasons set out in the Background. PPI representatives need individual preparation and support to contribute their knowledge of acceptability, lived experience, and equity considerations on equal terms with professional participants. In this study individual pre-workshop meetings were held with each PPI participant, a terminology document was developed and updated throughout the workshops, and PPI votes were weighted equally with professional votes throughout.

The supplementary materials include a pre-process team readiness checklist covering skill composition, role allocation, and stakeholder recruitment.

Stakeholder identification and recruitment

Fifteen stakeholders participated across the three rounds. Purposive sampling ensured representation across the domains required for viable MSU operation: stroke neurology, emergency medicine, pre-hospital care and ambulance service operations, stroke nursing, neuroradiology, and patient and public involvement. Recruitment aimed for a group small enough for structured facilitation while large enough to represent the diversity of perspectives that operational viability requires.

PPI representatives (n=6, comprising 40-43% of participants across rounds) were recruited through the Stroke Association. Individual pre-workshop meetings were held with each PPI participant by LM. All votes were weighted equally throughout the process. Subgroup analysis of PPI versus professional votes was not conducted as sample size was insufficient; this is recommended as a methodological development priority for future applications.

The uncertainty classification framework

Uncertainty in model-based decision support takes different forms that require different analytical responses. Walker et al. [26] distinguish uncertainty by where it arises in a model, how deep it runs, and whether it is reducible through better evidence or reflects genuine indeterminacy. In HTA, parameter uncertainty is addressed through probabilistic sensitivity analysis and structural uncertainty through scenario analysis [1, 2, 3, 4].

Existing HTA frameworks assume researchers already have a defensible operational structure. They provide guidance on parameter estimation, scenario construction, and uncertainty reporting, but not on how to establish the operational structure itself when an innovation does not yet exist. The methodology described here addresses this earlier problem: it generates the operational architecture that HTA uncertainty analysis then populates.

The Walker et al. distinction is applied to pre-implementation operational specification. Three categories are defined, presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Uncertainty classification framework

Category	Definition	Relationship to Walker et al. typology	Analytical response in HTA
Second-order uncertainty (parameter imprecision)	Stakeholders agree on operational approach but cannot specify precise parameter values	Corresponds to statistical and scenario uncertainty: reducible in principle through better evidence	Probabilistic sensitivity analysis over stakeholder-endorsed parameter ranges [4]
Third-order uncertainty (structural choice)	Stakeholders cannot agree on the operational approach itself: genuine alternative models of how the innovation could work	Corresponds to deep uncertainty: not resolvable by more data; reflects divergent contextual judgements or values	Scenario analysis comparing alternative operational structures with transparent documentation of what drove the structural choice
Irreducible trade-offs	Competing priorities with no objectively correct resolution: clinical ideal vs operational feasibility; equity vs efficiency	Beyond the Walker et al. typology: not resolvable by evidence or local adaptation; requires explicit value judgements	Explicit documentation of trade-off, vote distributions, and rationale enabling decision-makers to assess value alignment

PSA = probabilistic sensitivity analysis. HTA = health technology assessment.

Third-order uncertainties vary in their temporal structure. Some are inherently structural: they reflect value conflicts unlikely to be resolved by changes in evidence or circumstances. Others are contingent: they reflect the current state of knowledge, service configuration, or technology, and may resolve as context evolves. In the MSU application, the base location trade-off was classified as inherently structural, while operating hours non-consensus was identified as contingent on current thrombectomy service provision. This distinction matters for implementation planning, where contingent uncertainties can be flagged for review when relevant conditions change.

In this study, the research team classified non-consensus items after Round 3 by re-examining transcripts deductively, following participants' own reasoning. We recommend that future applications include independent double-classification of non-consensus items and identify this as a priority for further methodological work.

Workshop structure and conduct

Three online workshops were conducted using Microsoft Teams and Miro for real-time collaborative documentation. Online delivery was selected to enable participation from stakeholders across England and Wales and to support replicability in contexts where face-to-face workshops are impractical.

Round 1: Domain generation

Round 1 identified the operational domains requiring specification. Following silent generation, participants shared elements in round-robin format, which were grouped thematically by the facilitation team in real time. No voting occurred in Round 1. The output was an agreed framework of operational domains for subsequent specification.

Round 2: Specification development

Round 2 developed specific proposals for each operational domain. Participants discussed options, considered evidence from international MSU services and analogous pre-hospital innovations, and moved toward proposed specifications documented in real time. Round 2 generated draft specifications for each domain, with areas of disagreement noted for Round 3.

Round 3: Consensus assessment

Round 3 assessed consensus on the specifications developed in Round 2. Each of the 20 operational elements was presented with its proposed specification. Participants rated agreement on a five-point Likert scale, with a formal option to indicate insufficient knowledge to vote on a specific item. A pre-specified threshold of 80% agreement was applied, consistent with established NGT and Delphi practice [8, 9]. Participant checking was conducted between Rounds 2 and 3, with emerging specifications circulated for comment before the consensus survey was administered.

Supplemental interviews

Where participants could not attend workshops, supplemental individual interviews were conducted post-workshop in each round. In Round 1, interviews lasted between 28 and 76 minutes (mean 48 minutes); in Round 2, between 39 and 75 minutes (mean 58 minutes); in Round 3, between 59 and 88 minutes (mean 78 minutes). Researchers shared viewpoints and emerging themes from the workshop as discussion prompts, allowing interview participants to respond to the group discussion they had not attended.

The principal risk is anchoring: interview participants receiving workshop viewpoints as prompts may converge toward positions that emerged in group discussion rather than contributing independent perspectives. Mitigation included presenting multiple viewpoints rather than a single emerging consensus, and the iterative multi-round structure which allowed positions to evolve across rounds.

Data collection and analysis

Qualitative analysis was an ongoing process across all three rounds. Round 1 data were analysed thematically to identify and group operational domains. For Rounds 2 and 3, framework analysis was used [20], enabling systematic charting of participant views against the developing operational pathway. Framework analysis was selected because it allows analysis to be both inductive and structured around the analytical questions driving the study. Analysis was led by LM using NVivo 12.

The transition from qualitative synthesis in Rounds 1 and 2 to quantitative consensus survey in Round 3 was a deliberate design choice. Qualitative methods in the earlier rounds captured the reasoning behind participant positions, not just the positions themselves. This was essential for the uncertainty classification in Round 3. The survey then provided a

simultaneous, transparent record of the distribution of views across all participants, preventing the dominance effects that can occur in purely discursive processes.

Following completion of the final pathway, transcripts were re-examined deductively by LM and JS to identify and classify all documented uncertainties and trade-offs [18]. This separation of pathway development analysis from uncertainty classification was intentional: it allowed classification to be applied systematically to the completed pathway.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was provided via Northumbria University ethics online system (reference: 4117). The study was deemed by the Health Research Authority (HRA) to not require HRA approval. All participants were provided with a detailed information sheet prior to the study and provided signed consent to participate.

Results

Participants

Fifteen participants took part in Round 1, with 14 participating in each of Rounds 2 and 3. One participant who attended Round 1 was unable to attend subsequent rounds. Supplemental interviews were conducted with one participant across all three rounds. Table 4 presents participant details.

Table 4: Study participants across three rounds [18]

Role	Organisation / background	Round 1	Round 2	Round 3
Stroke physician (x2)	NHS Comprehensive Stroke Centres	Yes	Yes	Yes
Emergency physician	NHS Emergency Department	Yes	Yes	Yes
Paramedic / pre-hospital clinician (x2)	NHS Ambulance Service	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ambulance operations manager	NHS Ambulance Service	Yes	Interview	Yes
Stroke nurse specialist	NHS Stroke Service	Yes	Yes	Yes
Neuroradiologist	NHS Comprehensive Stroke Centre	Interview	Interview	Interview
Stroke commissioner	NHS England	Yes	Yes	Yes
PPI representative (x6)	Stroke Association / stroke survivors and carers	Yes	Yes	Yes
Total participants		15	14	14

PPI = patient and public involvement. Source: Moseley et al. [18].

Round 1: Operational domains identified

Round 1 generated eight operational domains requiring specification for a viable MSU service, presented in Table 5. The domains reflect the breadth of decision-making required before implementation, from immediate operational decisions about dispatch and staffing to broader questions about service integration and equity of access.

Table 5: Operational domains identified in Round 1 [18]

Domain	Key elements identified
Dispatch	Criteria for MSU activation; dual dispatch protocols; rendezvous with standard ambulance; geographic coverage area
Staffing and crewing	Clinical skill mix on board; telemedicine versus on-board physician; paramedic scope of practice; training requirements
Imaging and diagnosis	CT versus CT-A capability; point of care testing; scan interpretation (on-board versus telemedicine)
Treatment eligibility	IVT criteria; LVO identification; contraindication management; stroke mimic protocols
Conveyance	Post-treatment destination; bypass of local hospitals; direct to CSC versus local hospital
Service integration	Handover protocols; integration with existing ambulance dispatch; data sharing; quality assurance
Infrastructure and base	Vehicle basing location (CSC versus ambulance station); operating hours; service radius
Equity and access	Rural versus urban coverage; equity of access; population served

Source: Moseley et al. [18].

Round 2: Pathway development

Round 2 developed draft specifications for each of the eight operational domains. Two pathway configurations emerged as the principal alternatives. Pathway 1 based the MSU at a Comprehensive Stroke Centre, optimising proximity to thrombectomy services and specialist staff but concentrating the resource in areas where stroke care was already strongest. Pathway 2 based the MSU at an ambulance station, enabling dynamic deployment across a wider geographic area and better serving rural populations but introducing greater logistical complexity. Both reached sufficient internal coherence to warrant formal consensus assessment in Round 3, reflecting genuine uncertainty about optimal base location that required stakeholder adjudication rather than researcher determination. Full pathway documentation is available in Moseley et al. [18].

Round 3: Consensus outcomes

Twenty operational elements were assessed in Round 3. Table 6 presents all elements with agreed specifications and percentage agreement. Fourteen elements (70%) reached the 80% threshold, providing a defensible structural foundation for subsequent economic modelling [19]. Six elements did not reach threshold and are marked with an asterisk.

Table 6: Round 3 consensus results across all 20 operational elements [18]

Operational element	Agreed specification	% agreement
DISPATCH		
MSU activation criteria	MSU activated for all suspected strokes within defined geographic radius, using existing ambulance dispatch criteria	93%
Dual dispatch	Standard ambulance dispatched alongside MSU; MSU can stand down if stroke excluded	72%*
Rendezvous en route	Rendezvous with standard ambulance permitted for rural calls where standard ambulance reaches patient first	79%*
STAFFING		
Core clinical crew	Paramedic plus Critical Care Paramedic or equivalent as minimum crew	87%
Telemedicine	Telemedicine link to stroke physician for scan interpretation and treatment decisions	93%
Telemedicine fallback	Protocol for reversion to standard care if telemedicine unavailable	65%*
IMAGING AND DIAGNOSIS		
CT scanner on board	CT scanner required as minimum; CT-A desirable where feasible	87%
Scan interpretation	Telemedicine used for primary scan interpretation; AI decision support as adjunct	93%
Point of care testing	Blood testing on board to support IVT eligibility decisions	100%
TREATMENT		
IVT administration	IVT administered on scene where eligible, following standard criteria	100%
LVO identification	CT-A used to identify LVO where available; telemedicine review of images	87%
Contraindication management	Standard NHS IVT contraindication criteria apply	93%
Stroke mimic protocol	Specific protocol for managing stroke mimics identified on scene	87%
CONVEYANCE		
Post-IVT destination	Direct conveyance to CSC following IVT for all patients	93%
LVO conveyance	Direct to CSC bypass of local hospital for confirmed or suspected LVO	100%
No-IVT conveyance	Standard conveyance to nearest appropriate unit where IVT not given	87%
INFRASTRUCTURE		
Base location	MSU based at ambulance station to enable flexible deployment	71%*

Operational element	Agreed specification	% agreement
Operating hours	Hours aligned with local thrombectomy service hours	79%*
Overall viability: Pathway 1 (CSC-based)	Viable pathway based at CSC	62%*
Overall viability: Pathway 2 (ambulance-based)	Viable pathway based at ambulance station	85%

* Did not reach pre-specified 80% consensus threshold. Source: Moseley et al. [18].

Systematic classification of non-consensus items

Six of the 20 operational elements did not reach the 80% threshold. These items are not failures of the process. They are the process working as intended, surfacing genuine uncertainty and value disagreement that would otherwise be embedded silently in model assumptions. Table 7 presents all six items with vote distributions, uncertainty classification, rationale, and modelling implications.

Table 7: Systematic classification of non-consensus items from Round 3 (n=14 participants; consensus threshold 80%)

Item	Vote distribution	Classification	Rationale	Modelling implications
1. Base location of MSU	29% CSC; 71% ambulance station	Irreducible trade-off (inherently structural)	Genuinely competing values: efficiency (CSC-basing maximises patient volume) versus equity (ambulance-basing enables dynamic positioning to underserved areas). Participants described this as a value choice not resolvable by evidence. Ambulance-based Pathway 2 reached viability consensus (85%); CSC-based Pathway 1 did not (62%).	Scenario analyses comparing CSC-based and ambulance-based models. Demand modelling by individual ambulance services to optimise equity-efficiency balance. Decision-makers must assess value alignment. [18, 19]
2. Operating hours	79% agree	Third-order uncertainty (contingent)	Genuine uncertainty about overnight justification given low overnight stroke incidence and 24/7 staffing challenge. Contingent on current thrombectomy service provision: movement toward 24/7 access is likely to resolve this over time.	Scenario analysis comparing restricted-hours versus 24/7 operational models. Flag for review when local thrombectomy service hours change. [19]
3. Dual dispatch (MSU plus standard ambulance)	72% agree	Third-order uncertainty	Clinical logic broadly supported but non-consensus arose from concern about committing two resources under current NHS ambulance service pressures. HEMS dispatch precedent noted by those	Model dual dispatch versus single dispatch as alternative operational structures. Key parameters: stroke mimic rate, stand-down time, opportunity cost of committed ambulance resource. [18, 19]

Item	Vote distribution	Classification	Rationale	Modelling implications
			with dispatch experience; contested by others.	
4. Ambulance-MSU rendezvous en route	79% agree	Third-order uncertainty	Valued for rural settings where standard ambulance reaches patient faster. Non-consensus reflected logistical complexity and dispatch burden concerns. Participants with HEMS dispatch experience were more confident this is manageable.	Treat as locally determined structural choice. Economic and simulation models should allow rendezvous as an optional pathway feature with local calibration. [19]
5. Telemedicine fallback to standard care	65% agree	Third-order uncertainty (level of specification)	Disagreement was not with having a contingency but with specifying it as a blanket national protocol. Local clinical judgement should determine the response. Reveals a boundary condition: some specifications must be left to local implementation. Contingent on current connectivity infrastructure.	Model as a locally determined parameter. Sensitivity analyses should test impact of varying telemedicine unavailability rates. Flag for review as connectivity infrastructure improves. [18]
6. Overall viability of CSC-based Pathway 1	62% agree on viability	Third-order uncertainty	Meta-level assessment of the CSC-based operational model as a whole. Failure reflects accumulated concerns about CSC dispatch capability and geographic concentration in areas where stroke care is already strong.	CSC-based and ambulance-based pathways should be modelled as distinct scenarios. The 85% consensus on ambulance-based viability provides the defensible structural foundation for primary economic modelling. [18, 19]

CSC = Comprehensive Stroke Centre. Contingent = uncertainty likely to resolve as context changes. Inherently structural = value conflict unlikely to be resolved by changes in evidence or circumstances. Classifications applied by research team (LM, JS) deductively from Round 3 transcripts.

Five of the six items represent third-order uncertainty: structural choices that depend on local context or values and cannot be resolved by better evidence. Only one, base location, represents an irreducible trade-off, a conflict between equity and efficiency that participants described as unresolvable by technical means. No items were classified as second-order uncertainty. Where disagreement existed it was consistently about the operational approach rather than about parameter values.

Item 5 (the telemedicine fallback) is worth noting separately. Participants were not disagreeing with the principle of a contingency protocol but with specifying it as a blanket national rule, arguing that local clinical judgement should determine the response. This illustrates a boundary condition for the methodology: some specifications must be left to local implementation. That boundary is itself a useful output for those planning implementation or designing evaluations.

The two items that fell just below the threshold (operating hours and ambulance rendezvous, both at 79%) missed consensus for substantive reasons rather than statistical noise. Both should be treated as third-order uncertainties requiring scenario analysis, not as settled parameters that narrowly missed a cut-off.

Discussion

What SCOPE adds

This paper describes SCOPE (Stakeholder Consensus for Operational Pre-implementation Evidence), a methodology developed to address a problem that existing consensus methods, expert elicitation frameworks, and co-design approaches each approach but none fully resolves: how to generate defensible operational specifications for health innovations before implementation begins. The MSU application demonstrates that SCOPE can do this in a complex, multi-stakeholder context, achieving consensus on 14 of 20 operational elements and producing a systematic, auditable classification of the six non-consensus items. The resulting pathway provided the structural foundation for subsequent economic modelling [19], with each non-consensus item translated directly into a specific modelling decision.

Three process features were essential to this outcome. The sequential multi-round structure allowed interconnected decisions to be developed iteratively: decisions about dispatch and staffing in Round 2 directly shaped the treatment and conveyance decisions addressed in Round 3 in a way that a single-session NGT or sequential Delphi could not have managed. The mixed stakeholder composition ensured that equity and acceptability considerations were present from the outset: the geographic equity dimension of the base location decision was articulated most clearly by PPI representatives. The real-time documentation on the shared digital whiteboard gave participants immediate visibility of how their contributions were being interpreted, enabling correction in the moment.

SCOPE also reduces the burden on local implementation teams. The consensus specifications produced through a national or regional process provide a validated operational foundation that local commissioners and research teams can adopt directly, without repeating the full stakeholder process from scratch. Where local adaptation is needed, the systematic classification of non-consensus items identifies precisely where it is. A rural ambulance service considering MSU deployment does not need to re-examine whether IVT should be administered on scene. It does need to work through the base location trade-off for its specific geography. SCOPE tells it which decision that is, why it is genuinely difficult, and what modelling would help resolve it.

Methodological heritage and contribution

NGT was developed by Delbecq, Van de Ven, and Gustafson for programme planning contexts where groups needed to generate and prioritise ideas systematically without the

dominance effects of unstructured discussion [5]. Applied to clinical appropriateness decisions, NGT proved effective at surfacing the distribution of expert opinion on questions with defensible answers [6, 7, 8, 9].

The limitations of NGT for operational design become apparent when the question shifts from appropriateness to specification. Appropriateness questions have a bounded solution space and a single session can cover many items. Operational specification questions are structurally different: the answer space is wide, decisions are interconnected, and the relevant knowledge is distributed across professional and patient communities who do not share a common frame of reference. A single NGT session can produce a priority list. It cannot produce a coherent operational pathway.

Delphi methods originated as forecasting tools outside healthcare and address some limitations of single-pass methods through iteration, but sacrifice the face-to-face discussion that allows participants to understand and respond to each other's reasoning rather than simply voting on pre-formulated propositions [8, 9]. Co-design approaches provide the participatory depth and patient centredness that both NGT and Delphi lack, but were developed primarily for improving existing services and do not typically produce the structured consensus record that HTA credibility requires [13, 14].

SCOPE draws on all three traditions. From NGT it takes structured facilitation, individual voting to quantify consensus, and the discipline of separating generation from evaluation. From Delphi it takes iterative refinement and participant checking between rounds. From co-design it takes the principle that patients and professionals bring qualitatively different and equally necessary knowledge to operational design. The modifications SCOPE makes to this combined inheritance are specific responses to specific limitations. The multi-round structure addresses the complexity of interconnected decisions. The uncertainty classification framework translates consensus outcomes into modelling decisions. The auditable documentation trail gives the process evidentiary status that informal expert consultation lacks.

Locating SCOPE within the health innovation development pathway clarifies what it does and what it does not do. Upstream methods assess whether an innovation is worth pursuing. Downstream methods evaluate and operationalise an innovation whose structure has been determined. SCOPE occupies the space between: it translates a promising innovation concept into a specified operational model that can be evaluated, costed, and implemented. Without it, the transition from upstream assessment to downstream evaluation rests on assumptions that are neither empirically derived nor stakeholder-endorsed.

The value of that transition has been characterised in terms of what is lost when an effective intervention fails to reach the patients who would benefit, or reaches them inconsistently. SCOPE does not quantify that value, which belongs in economic evaluation and budget impact analysis once the modelled pathway has been assessed. What SCOPE does is

reduce the risk that implementation will fail or underperform because the operational assumptions underpinning the model were wrong.

Relationship to structured expert elicitation

Structured expert elicitation frameworks including the Sheffield Elicitation Framework (SHELF [27]) and the STEER approach in NICE guidance provide rigorous methods for quantifying parameter uncertainty in HTA models. These are methodologically adjacent to SCOPE but solve a different problem. SHELF is used after operational structure has been determined. SCOPE is used before: it determines what the operational structure should be.

The two methods are complementary. SCOPE produces the structural foundation that SHELF then populates. In a complete evidence development workflow, SCOPE would precede SHELF: second-order uncertainties identified in Round 3 become candidates for formal SHELF elicitation, and third-order uncertainties define the alternative structural scenarios across which SHELF elicitation would be conducted separately.

SCOPE does not replace expert elicitation for parameter estimation. It provides the operational foundation that makes subsequent elicitation defensible. The sequence is: SCOPE then SHELF then economic model then HTA submission.

SCOPE and pathway innovation

SCOPE was developed in response to a specific problem: pathway innovations cannot draw on observed operational data in the way that technology substitution can. When one drug replaces another, the comparator exists and can be measured. When a new care pathway is created, it has not existed before. Every operational parameter represents a prospective choice, not a retrospective observation.

The MSU application illustrates the consequences of this for modelling. The dispatch model, staffing configuration, operating hours, base location, and conveyance protocols that feed into the economic model [19] could not be derived from observation of existing practice. They had to be specified prospectively. Without SCOPE, each would have been a researcher assumption open to challenge. With SCOPE, each is either a stakeholder-endorsed specification or a documented uncertainty with a defined analytical response.

Major clinical advances rarely arrive alone. Mechanical thrombectomy generated not one operational design challenge but several: MSUs, video triage, point-of-care testing including D-dimer assays, and AI-assisted scan interpretation each represent a distinct pathway innovation requiring operational specification before evaluation. Research teams working in areas of active clinical innovation should expect cascades of interconnected operational design problems rather than single isolated ones.

SCOPE's value is greatest where existing evidence development methods are weakest: pathway innovations creating new care models, service reconfigurations without direct comparators, and technology-enabled services whose operational form is genuinely undetermined before implementation. For innovations where operational parameters can be

derived from existing service data, simpler approaches may suffice. The decision framework in the supplementary materials is intended to help research teams make that judgement.

Temporal and contextual validity

SCOPE specifications are of their time and place. This is a methodological reality to be stated explicitly, not a limitation to be apologised for.

The consensus specifications represent the best available stakeholder knowledge at a defined point in time, in a defined health system context. Some will remain stable as context changes. Others will not. In the MSU application, participants noted that the operating hours non-consensus reflected the current state of thrombectomy service provision and that movement toward 24/7 access would likely resolve it. That uncertainty is contingent on current circumstances, not inherently structural.

We recommend that SCOPE outputs include an explicit statement of the contextual conditions under which consensus was reached, and that specifications be flagged for review when those conditions change materially. In the stroke context, triggers for review would include significant changes to thrombectomy service configuration, advances in point-of-care testing that alter triage decisions, or changes to ambulance service geography or resourcing. Each represents a cascade innovation that may not only generate new SCOPE questions but update answers from previous processes.

Specifications produced for NHS England and Wales reflect the particular configuration of that health system. Transferring them to a different health system requires either a new process grounded in that context or a structured assessment of which specifications are context-independent and which are system-specific.

Resource requirements

SCOPE requires a realistic investment of researcher and participant time. In the MSU application the process ran for approximately six months from initial stakeholder recruitment to completion of Round 3 analysis. Participants contributed approximately seven hours across three workshops, plus one to two hours for those who took part in supplemental interviews. Between-round activities accounted for the majority of researcher time.

Software costs were low: Microsoft Teams, Miro (free tier sufficient), NVivo, and standard online survey tools.

The team composition required extends beyond what is typically assembled for HTA modelling or evidence development projects, as described in the Methods. Teams lacking the necessary combination of qualitative facilitation, qualitative analysis, clinical, and modelling skills should seek partnership rather than attempting to adapt the process to a less complete team. A poorly facilitated process risks producing apparent consensus that does not reflect genuine agreement. A process conducted without modelling input risks producing specifications that are clinically coherent but analytically unusable.

Compared to a standard two-round Delphi, SCOPE requires more researcher time but produces something qualitatively different: face-to-face discussion that allows disagreement to be explored, mixed stakeholder composition that surfaces equity and acceptability considerations, and systematic uncertainty classification that informs subsequent modelling. For projects where model structure credibility matters, that investment is proportionate to what is at stake.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. The methodology was developed and tested in a single context: MSU pathway development for NHS England and Wales. While we have argued for its generalisability to other pathway innovations, replication in different health system contexts and with different innovation types is needed to establish the method's transferability and to identify where adaptation may be required.

Participant numbers were sufficient for structured facilitation but limited subgroup analysis. Fourteen to fifteen participants across three rounds is consistent with NGT guidance, but it means that the influence of specific stakeholder groups on consensus outcomes could not be formally assessed. PPI representatives comprised 40-43% of participants across rounds. Whether their inclusion materially changed consensus outcomes cannot be determined from this study; we recommend sensitivity analysis comparing consensus outcomes with and without PPI votes as standard practice for future applications.

The supplemental interview approach introduces a risk of anchoring, as interview participants received workshop viewpoints as discussion prompts. Mitigation strategies are described in the Methods, but the potential influence of this on the positions taken by interview participants cannot be fully excluded.

The study was conducted entirely online. While this supported broad geographic participation, it may have affected the quality of real-time facilitation and documentation compared to face-to-face delivery. Future work should examine whether online and face-to-face delivery produce comparable outputs.

The uncertainty classification in this study was conducted by the research team rather than through independent double-classification. While classification followed participants' own articulated reasoning, inter-rater reliability was not formally assessed. We identify this as a priority for future applications.

Conclusions

SCOPE provides a systematic methodology for the operational co-development of health innovations before implementation, addressing a gap that existing evidence development frameworks, consensus methods, and expert elicitation approaches do not fill. By grounding

operational assumptions in documented stakeholder consensus, SCOPE gives HTA and evaluation models a structural foundation that can withstand independent scrutiny.

Pearl establishes that causal model structure must be asserted, not discovered. In pre-implementation contexts where no outcome data exists and system complexity means no single expert holds sufficient knowledge, SCOPE provides the structured, transparent, and auditable method for eliciting and aggregating the distributed knowledge on which valid model specification depends. The iterative three-round structure is not a methodological convenience. It is what the complexity of the problem requires.

SCOPE sits upstream of both structured expert elicitation and implementation science methods. It generates the operational structure that expert elicitation then populates with quantified parameter uncertainty, and that implementation science methods then address in terms of how to implement effectively.

Implementation cannot wait for perfect information. The value of SCOPE is not that it eliminates uncertainty before a service is designed or evaluated. It is that it makes uncertainty explicit, classifiable, and tractable. Decision-makers know what has been agreed and on what basis. They know what remains uncertain and what kind of uncertainty it is. They know where value trade-offs have been made and what values were in tension. That transparency is what allows implementation to proceed responsibly rather than either stalling indefinitely or proceeding on unexamined assumptions.

SCOPE's outputs also serve commissioners and local implementation teams directly. The consensus specifications provide a validated starting point that localities can adopt without repeating the full process. The classification of non-consensus items provides a structured decision framework, identifying what kind of uncertainty remains, what value trade-offs are embedded in the decision, and what analytical work would inform a locally appropriate choice.

SCOPE also has implications for those making resource allocation decisions about emerging health innovations. Research funders deciding whether to commission a full evaluation, commissioners considering whether to pilot a new service, and HTA bodies assessing an economic model all face the same problem: operational assumptions they cannot independently verify. SCOPE makes those assumptions visible, documented, and stakeholder-endorsed. For pathway innovations, where no operational comparator exists, it shifts the question from whether we trust the researchers to whether we agree with the stakeholders. That is a more tractable and more legitimate basis for investment decisions.

The methodology is applicable to any health innovation sharing the key features: it does not yet exist in the target context; multiple professional and patient perspectives must be integrated; specifications must be detailed enough for modelling but flexible enough for local adaptation; and uncertainty classification is needed to guide analytical choices.

Implementation resources are provided as supplementary materials, including round-by-

round protocols, a pre-process team readiness checklist, an uncertainty classification decision aid, and a reporting checklist aligned with ACCORD [25].

Declarations

Availability of data and materials

The qualitative data generated during this study are not publicly available as participants did not give consent for data sharing and the full dataset contains identifying information. The authors would be happy to interrogate the data on behalf of others upon reasonable request and subject to necessary ethical approvals. The SCOPE protocols, templates, and toolkit are freely available as supplementary materials.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

PM, JS, MA conceived the study and SCOPE methodology. PM, JS, LM, MA designed the study protocol. JS, LM led data collection with input from PM, MA, GM, LP. LM, JS conducted data analysis. PM, JS, LM, MA, SG developed the SCOPE methodology and toolkit. PM, JS drafted the manuscript. All authors contributed to interpretation, reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

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Abbreviations

ACCORD ACcurate COnsensus Reporting Document

AI Artificial Intelligence

CSC Comprehensive Stroke Centre

CT Computed Tomography
CT-A Computed Tomography Angiography
HEMS Helicopter Emergency Medical Service
HTA Health Technology Assessment
IVT Intravenous Thrombolysis
LVO Large Vessel Occlusion
MSU Mobile Stroke Unit
NASSS Non-Adoption, Abandonment, Scale-up, Spread, Sustainability
NGT Nominal Group Technique
NHS National Health Service
PPI Patient and Public Involvement
PSA Probabilistic Sensitivity Analysis
SCOPE Stakeholder Consensus for Operational Pre-implementation Evidence
SHELF Sheffield Elicitation Framework

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